

Fundamentals of Conciliation in Cases of Trust-Deficit, when Everyone is just Mendacious

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ABSTRACT

Reconstruction of trust is a basic existential necessity. Petty, as it may sound- but today all people want just to trust and be trusted. Colonial conquest completely obliterated ability to trust and be trusted. As a result the fast paced globalisation project can easily be reduced into; *"one big animal farm- where all people are equal, but some people more equal than others"*

Trust is the missing cornerstone for resolving all our historic injustices. If only people could fostering a society capable of truth, peace and selfless development of the planet. The planet rewards all those who diligently serve it. In South Africa—and globally—centuries of colonization have left a legacy of distrust that undermines efforts at reconciliation and growth. Trust reconstruction requires moving beyond traditional methods of conflict resolution that have consistently failed to address the root causes of inequality and discord. This article examines the enduring influence of colonialism in South Africa, focusing on its systemic role in perpetuating inequality, mistrust, and conflict. It critiques the judicial system and legal fraternity for enabling post-colonial conflicts and challenges politicians to confront their reliance on colonial strategies. Highlighting the shift from overt colonialism to covert systems of control post-World War II, the article frames ongoing socio-economic crises and mistrust as deliberate colonial legacies.

Analyzing South Africa's historical eras—spanning Dutch, British, Boer, apartheid, and democratic periods—the article explores how colonialism systematically dismantled Indigenous values like *Ubuntu*, replacing them with exploitative systems that foster division. It critiques policies like Black Economic Empowerment, arguing for more inclusive legislation that promotes sustainable generational wealth and social mobility.

Employing historical analysis, systemic critique, and legal reasoning, the study exposes the failure of current legal and policy frameworks to address conflicts rooted in colonial designs. It advocates for a paradigm shift where colonizers and the colonized engage in truth-based dialogue, relinquishing both power and authority to build a trust-based society. Finally, it calls for alternative dispute resolution mechanisms prioritizing trust, fairness, and historical justice to achieve sustainable and equitable development.

INTRODUCTION

Rebuilding trust is the cornerstone of resolving historical injustices and fostering a society capable of sustained peace and upward social mobility. In South Africa—and globally—centuries of colonization have left a legacy of distrust that undermines efforts at reconciliation and growth. Trust reconstruction requires moving beyond traditional methods of conflict resolution that have consistently failed to address the root causes of inequality and discord.

To South Africans, this means prioritizing inclusive and transformative policies that bridge racial and economic divides. South Africa must shift from frameworks that focus on unsustainable individualised wealth accumulation to systems that promote generational upward social mobility. Legal and policy reforms should embrace restorative justice, acknowledgement of historic wrongs by colonisers. Make provision of mechanisms for healing and trust reconstruction post-colonial conflicts.

Calls for Empire's paradigm shift must be understood in proper context. The context began when coloniser used combat to invade and colonise a particular territory that was foreign to them. The coloniser sized power and authority over the conquered territory. 400 years later the coloniser is still positioned as custodian of the territory. Through education and political system that has been established by the coloniser, public is successfully led to believe colonisation has completely ended. This public belief makes the public to be complacent with covert colonisation. What is even worse is that public naiveness is not only aiding perpetual colonisation, defend it.

As such the coloniser is involve in every political activity occurring in all their colonies. Colonial involvement in political affairs of sovereign territory is indicative of refusal to release colonial power and authority. As purported by political and education that colonisation ended. This purported end of colonisation was a decision of UN. UN charter was developed by the coloniser. Subsequently, colonisation came to an abrupt end in compliance to UN declaration. Therefore, safe to conclude that the end of colonisation was in fact voluntary. The coloniser had full discretion in how they choose to end colonisation.

As such the coloniser selected to unbundle colonisation into elements of colonisation. The unbundling of colonisation created colonial power and colonial authority. Colonizer branded colonial power as sovereignty. NATO was then established through UN for purposes of protecting sovereignty. As such NATO was set up to protect colonies on behalf of the coloniser. Supplementary to UN and NATO additional international institutions such as USAID, WHO, WB, IMF, INICEF, Global Ranking Agencies etc. These organisation function as covert colonial agents (or proxy). They exert colonial authority in the form of conditions for recognition for access to economic network. The post world war II international organisations are vectors of colonial authority. The international organisations define policies that are prerequisite for sovereign recognition. The international organisations pen the details of prerequisite policies in the form of conventions and protocols. Sovereign states are coerced to comply- in the pretence of protecting human rights. The fundamental human right is equality. But the founding principles such as VITO powers reflect their

inability to uphold the values they claim to promote. The policies of these international organisations are designed to dictate who rules, when s/he rules, how s/he rule, and why s/he rules. This renders conventions and protocols as colonial authority and who, when, how, and why s/he rules is a rented power of colonial rule with or without his or her knowledge. These conventions and protocols must be subjected to national scrutiny. They must be measured through traditional values of Ubuntu. They must pass the test of family, honesty, fairness, mutual respect, and empowerment. Global institutions start understanding the importance of a family. The day their policies start focusing on strengthening and empowering families. Is the day the world will be free from conflicts, trust deficit and equal. Every species is born in a family. Family is the closest way to secure people support for success. The western obsession with individualism is a feudal culture. It is primitive. It is colonial. It is designed to perpetuate everything that is wrong- mistrust, disputes, conflicts, inequalities, slavery and violence.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

The obvious problem in South African context is inequality. South African inequality purely represents an abuser-abused relationship. Colonisers are abusers. Africans are abused. Coloniser-colonised abuse relationship has deteriorated trust. The country suffers serious trust issues. South African trust issues cut very deep. Since 1652, there has never been a genuine effort to build trust between Europeans and Africans. The lack of trust between Africans and Europeans has spilled-over. Close to 400 years, Africans have been struggling to trust each other. Europeans are behind every conflict between Africans. In 1994, African were entrusted with political power. However, their political power is devoid of political authority. History demonstrate that Boers that are Dutch descendent were given political power by Britain from 1830 to 1994. For all those years with political power, they were devoid of political authority.

Democratic government developed an act called Black Economic Empowerment Act. This act is nothing but a deceit. Not even a single African family has benefited a generational wealth. Proper definition of economic empowerment is upward mobility. Economic empowerment is not measured by an individual's bank activity, asset portfolio, business ownership nor opulent lifestyle. Accurate indicator of economic empowerment is upward social mobility. Social mobility is generational. The past 30 years has demonstrated that South African black wealth does not translate to upward social mobility.

Black South Africans have adapted very interesting coping mechanisms. They have learnt to reduce and simplify every experience. For example, if you ask any indigenous South African; "what is colonization"? The answer will be; "colonization is an invasion. Invasion by tricksters. After their invasion, everything became a scam. Today South Africa has fraudsters, criminals, rapists and murderers- which principles that not fostered by cultural values of Ubuntu. Colonial transformation of African culture was systematic corrosion of Ubuntu.

Following the patterns of post-colonial countries. It is found that all post colonial country are struggling with either crime, violence or both. Additional to that, their correctional centres are described as most horrific in the world. Suggesting they are used to harden criminals and proliferate criminality. Indicative of collecting conflicts to centralize it, only to decentralize it. Then come back and report high re-offending rate. The article attempts will highlight why this coincident is consistent.

Law is an instrument of conflict resolution. Therefore, by extension lawyers are entrusted with conflict resolution responsibility. When unresolved conflicts accumulate and escalate, inferential reasoning would suggest maybe both the law and lawyers are struggling to settle disputes. The reason for the struggle could either be that the law is made to only resolve selected types of conflicts, or the lawyers are not adequately equipped to resolve certain conflicts. Suggesting lady justice is partially blind- and the rule of law is selective. Given that none of these

countries have published a report on historical justice litigation. This article hypothesise that law graduates are not adequately prepared to settle conflicts perpetrated by coloniser. Nor they are armed with sharp eye for identification of conflicts that are colonial craftsmanship or colonial modus operadi.

This article assert that colonisation was first conceived in the 15th century as a viable strategy for building and growing imperial countries. A strategy that was duplicated from nonhuman nature. Natural science would attest that everything is notorious of colonising or being colonised, pending to material conditions. At the same frequency, nature continue to stress that there is no species nor substance that have monopoly to colonising. Nature has taught and influenced human ancestors that to colonise is the way to go. What the current generation has learnt is that both the coloniser and the colonised become a colony of colonisation. The adverse of 4th industrial revolution has made it difficult for the coloniser to control the narrative of history. The coloniser now know that decisions they take today will be experienced by their offspring tomorrow. In as much they have always be aware of this, and managed it by mastering the science and art of erasing and re-writing history. Subsequently, this has escalated anxiety both the victor and the victim. Colonisers have been leasing out power and retaining authority. If coloniser wants to be happy- it must allow everyone to be happy. UK through USA must consider consider now leasing both power and authority. The leasing both power and authority will secure themselves a significant chair in critical economic networks.

If America can be hit at its currency their suffering is biologically experienced to be the same. They both suffer from elevated levels of cortisol and similar imbalance of neuro-chemicals. The current generation has learnt we no longer have to live like predators and parasites. This article hypothesise that both the coloniser and the colonised are trapped in colonisation lies- and want a way out. The only way out is when both the victor and the victim hold each other's hands out of primitive definition of a prosperous nation. More importantly, that both parties are prepared to hold each others hands and tell each other the truth without fear of victimisation.

Primarily, this article attempts to show how colonisation started all the lies. Secondary, the article presents a case to show why this era is a window opportunity for coloniser to not only lease out power but authority as well. Attempts to lay a foundation on how: lies can be turned into truth; suspicions into trust; conflicts into peace; and inequalities into inclusive equality.

After all we may need to accept almost everything known to man to day is built on the foundation of experience, knowledge and wisdom of our ancestors. All acquired through cognitive processes. These processes involved realistic, positive and critical analysis. Sometimes caught in a dilemma of what should be more acceptable between knowledge acquired from deductive or inductive process. Most of this knowledge was acquired before modern science- in appreciation of immune system, neuroscience, and artificial intelligence. Limitations of cognitive biases were among the limitations our forebears. However, those privileged to be alive today must not only find fault from the weaknesses of those who lived before us. We must appreciate the heritage they left us whether it is sweet, bitter or sour. We must appreciate that they were the closest to those who were civilized from "hunters and gatherers". That understanding will assist the current generation to understand that our ancestors only had nature as their school. Most if not all their knowledge was assimilated from the interaction, experience and observation of nature. Therefore Steward et. at. assertion should be viewed as such, when they say (1) colonization occurs in many fields, from the scientific to the philosophical, and involves all forms of life including flora, fauna and micro-organisms. All these forms of life can colonize or be colonized by others. Richard Schaefer (2) perceives colonialism as the most frequent way in which one group of people take an opportunity to dominate another. Bell characterise it as persistent political, social, economic, and cultural subjugation over people by a foreign power for an extended period (3). Smallwood (4) says this type of subjugation aims primarily to transform Indigenous People at all possible levels including population, health (mental/physical), social, spiritual, economic, and cultural levels. He goes as far as citing a string of scholars who argue that

colonization is racial, ethnic and cultural genocide. Evans-Campbell notes that colonialism is a product of wars, massacres, genocides, displacements, forced labor, forcible removal of children from their parents, residential schools, environmental destruction, intentional spread of deadly diseases, assimilations, and almost complete extermination of Indigenous social, cultural, and spiritual practices (5,6).

This article intends to advocate for a nation of Trust. To make South Africa Trust again. This is important because any society that lacks trust, that society becomes an infestation of conflicts. These conflicts are commonly neglected. Otherwise resolved with violence. Few of them are resolved through litigation. Recently, Alternative Conflict Resolution (ADR) is promoted as a more preferred option than conflict settlement through- sanctions, violence and litigation. However, every ADR requires both affected parties voluntarily participate to it. To ensure that ADR process is safe and fair to all parties affected. ADR process must have risk mitigation mechanism to protect affected parties that are vulnerable to imbalances from either; physical threat or financial abuse or psychological coercion. ADR ought draw its powers either from affected parties or Rule of Law (ROL) or Historical Justice Litigations (HJL). Someone or something must be trusted. If parties can not be trusted to ensure every conflict is resolved- then there must be a trusted process for resolving conflicts.

HYPOTHESIS

1. Law is entrusted with responsibility to avoid or to resolve conflicts. By extension lawyers are entrusted with conflict resolution. When unresolved conflicts accumulate, then both the law and lawyers are struggling to settle disputes. The cause for the struggle could either be that the law is made to only resolve selected types of conflicts, or the lawyers are equipped enough to resolve certain conflicts. This article hypothesise that law graduates are not

adequately equipped to settle conflicts that are creative-products of colonial modus operadi.

2. This article assert that colonisation was first conceived in the 15th century as a viable strategy in building and growing any country. This strategy was copied and pasted from nonhuman nature. Everything had potential to colonise. Nature did show that there is now species or substance that have monopoly to colonising. Nature has also taught ancestors that a colonizer can eventually be colonised. What UK leadership must now know is that both the coloniser and the colonised are a colony of colonisation. At biological level both the victor and the victim suffer similar mental inflammation. The experience of inflictions of cortisol and neuro inhibitors is the same. For example at mental health level poverty is a neuro inhibitory drug, so is aggrandizing. Mental condition is the same to both both the vulnerable and the powerful. Human are social species their strength is on co-operation and their weakness is on conflict. This article hypothesise that both the coloniser and the colonised are trapped in colonisation lies- and both want a way out. The only way out is when both the victor and the victim hold each other's hands out of primitive definition of a prosperous nation. More importantly, that both parties are prepared to hold each others hands and tell each other the truth without fear of victimisation.

METHODOLOGY

The methodology deployed in this research integrates a combination of philosophical reasoning frameworks. Most of them traditionally relied upon for legal adjudication and policy analysis. Such elements of assorted epistemology range from historical analysis to systemic critique of accepted boundaries.

Historical and Contextual Interpretation

Contextual Interpretation is used in this case to analyse the socio-political motivations, conditions, and consequences behind colonial and apartheid-era legislation.

Inductive Reasoning

General conclusions about set of issues such as colonial impacts by synthesizing data from multiple legislative acts and outcomes. The article intentionally most avoided historical patterns of dispossession, segregation, and marginalization across various laws. The observed patterns are generalized into overarching principles of colonial governance. The method allowed identification of consistent efforts across different statutes to restrict land ownership, enforce segregation, and undermine Indigenous social cohesion.

Analogical Reasoning

This technique allowed the article to compare the colonial strategies applied in South Africa to those in other post-colonial contexts. The deliberate effort to compare the character of South African colonisation in parison to other colonies lifted recycled colonial patterns. This type of reasoning enabled drawing of links between South African legislative impacts to global colonial strategy and tactics, like divide-and-rule tactics observed in Asia and other African nations. For example reflected on use of education laws to advance divide and conquer more than to foster development and

economic growth. Aside from South Africa, India being a typical case study of systemic suppression of Indigenous intellectual empowerment.

Purposive Interpretation

Purposive Interpretation proved to be essential for understanding the intent behind legislation, policies, and governance structures. The article interprets laws not just for their literal effects but for their intended purpose of maintaining systemic inequality and ensuring colonial authority. A case that stand out is the Population Registration Act of 1950 is analysed for its psychological abuse and social implications, beyond its role as a bureaucratic mechanism.

Textualism

Certain events had to be accepted as they are directly from the legislative text, prioritizing literal interpretations. This was important for testing processed against raw data. Such as data that displayed direct discrimination and provisions that formalized racial segregation. The Group Areas Act of 1950 as it is commonly critiqued for its explicit segregation mandates. This context extremely important for democratic government reflection of black economic empowerment act of 2003.

Precedent-Based Reasoning (Stare Decisis):

The article traces how apartheid legislation followed colonial legal principles, reflecting continuity in subjugation strategies. Stare decisis allowed analysis to explore how past British colonial legal decisions and frameworks influenced subsequent apartheid laws and governance practices. Historical links between the 1913 Natives Land Act and the 1950s segregation policies illustrate a lineage of systemic dispossession.

Golden Rule

Attempts were made to modify strict literal interpretations to avoid absurd outcomes. However, golden rule might not have been dispense enough. In several cases analysis was adjusted in interpretations to account for broader socio-political realities, ensuring coherence in critiquing colonial narratives. The areas that would be affected by golden rule would be the hypothesis section and characterised of apartheid laws as colonial laws.

Systemic Reasoning

The article situated relevant facts within the broader framework of colonisation as directly and indirectly abusive. Through systematic analysis available facts evaluated in the context of historical justice litigation and restorative justice between the colonised and coloniser. It is this type of reasoning that suggest the attachment of USAID to the doctrine of Rule of Law could undermine the sovereignty and its justice independence. Then instrumental in analysing its cascading impact on potential selective application of law as systematic strategy to corrode general territorial trust and fuelling of coordinated conflicts. It is through systematic reasoning that TRC as applied here in south Africa has been applied in other colonies- and in all these colonies it has never addressed TRC or conciliation process between the coloniser and the colonised.

Integrative Insights

The article integrates Enrique Dussel's "I conquer, therefore I am" philosophy to provide a theoretical foundation, tying colonial-era governance structures to global imperial ideologies. It highlights gaps in preparing legal practitioners to address colonial and systemic injustices. Proposes trust-building measures as a remedy for socio-political fractures, grounded in Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) principles. This methodology effectively uncovers the layered impacts of colonial laws, offering a comprehensive framework for understanding and challenging systemic inequalities.

It emphasizes both micro-level legal mechanisms and macro-level socio-political strategies that shaped South Africa's history and continue to influence its present.

CONSOLIDATION OF QUALITATIVE FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Rationalising Outcries Behind Artificial Red-tapes Within Legal Profession

Marc Welgemoed et al., conducted extensive analysis in South African on the gap between university legal education and legal practice. He found that there is a gap that supports a view that most law graduates are substantially underprepared for entry into legal practice. Higher education has always been accepted as crucial contributor to the economy. Due to their accepted role in developing knowledge and skilled graduates. However, mid-1990s saw heightened calls for measurable link between what is taught at higher education levels and the development of skills necessary for the working world. Arising from falsification of long sustained assumptions that graduates acquired sufficient skills during their academic years. Sufficiency in terms skills usefulness when they commence employment after leaving university (47). Motseotsile Marumoagae in 2021 highlighted the plight of underprivileged law graduates in South Africa in relation to the difficulties they experience when they attempt to access the legal profession. It demonstrates that, in addition to legislated requirements that they need to meet, they are also met with artificial requirements which are meant to effectively prevent them from accessing the legal profession (48).

Western Liberal Constitution

Access to justice for all in South Africa, is clearly set out in sections 34 and 35 of the *Constitution of the Republic of South Africa of 1996*. This access is necessary to improve living standards of all citizens. As a result the closest analysis of democratic South African constitution is by Erna Oliver and Willem H. Oliver in 2017 that define it as the most liberal constitutions in hand. To quote them; "*which 'guarantees the*

rights of individuals rather than collectives such as cultural and ethnic groups” (18). This is despite the admission of Bachmann et al in 2012 that colonialism has had a huge impact upon the legal systems of countries around the world. The historical impact of the British Empire can still be felt today in countries as diverse as Australia and South Africa (49). Bachmann et al goes to length about the writings after the fall of the Berlin Wall in 1989.

Fukuyama posited the “end of history”, the universalisation of Western liberal democracy as the final form of human government. Western liberal democracy has now been adopted by former colonies. The ideas of equal treatment under the law, individual rights and the rule of law. Underpinning this is the idea of legal certainty – that the law must be certain in order to ascertain rights and duties that are applied equally to all. However, the history of Western liberal democracy is inextricably linked to European colonialism. Indeed, the history and implications of the rise of liberal democracy in Europe, to be understood properly, must be read in conjunction with this colonial heritage. Liberal democracy’s development took place in this shadow; the legal systems of many countries around the world bear witness to this intertwined history. It is this intertwined relationship which gives rise to a dilemma. Dilemma arise from the imposition of a legal order that characterise empires and colonialism. Against the foundation of an independent legal order that marks the birth of the newly independent nation. The however the so called liberal constitutions are safely guarded to be rule of law that serves both masters (49).

European Rule of Law (EROL) and Historical Justice Litigation (HJL)”

Phenomena of “European Rule of Law (EROL)” is crafted to police the desired legal order to colonies (“post colonisation”). This desired legal order purports to secure independent legal order after independence. While the after effects suggest the EROL is diligently resourced to secure continued dependent legal order. The noise about the “Rule of Law” is amplified through USAID. Such funding is not available for “Historical Justice Litigation (HJL)”. “Historical Justice Litigation” is litigation which has at its aim the rectifying of past oppression in colonial (now postcolonial) states.

It is HJL that guarantee independent legal order. Independent legal order is essential for adherence to the self-same doctrine. This highlights the common inclination to formal interpretation of the “rule of law”- at the detriment of although it is a substantive adhered.

Ego Conquiro and Role of Certain international Organisations

Enrique Dussel’s concept, “I conquer, therefore I am” (*ego conquiro*), argues that colonialism was driven by a European-centric philosophy that justified conquest through a superiority complex. This ideology, which predates Descartes’ *cogito*, created an epistemological basis for naturalizing colonial domination (25). Scholars like Ferguson (1994), Cooper, and Packard argue that colonial legacies continue to shape and skew development agendas in former colonies. They critique international agencies (e.g., World Bank, USAID) for maintaining power asymmetries that hinder true empowerment in postcolonial societies (26). The rebranding of former colonies as “less developed countries” or “the Third World” further reflects persistent inequities (27).

Susceptibility of Ex-British Colonies to Violence

Historical evidence shows that ex-British colonies are more prone to inter-communal violence. The colonial policies are commonly implicated for fostering divisions. For example in South Asia and South Africa the colonial education system created a divide between English-medium and vernacular-medium schools. This exacerbate inequalities that persist through globalized English language dominance in former colonies like India, South Africa, and Sri Lanka (28, 29). Moreover, many postcolonial African rulers have adopted divide-and-rule tactics to maintain political power. Leaders like Mobutu Sese Seko, Thabo Mbeki, Jacob Zuma and Cyril Ramaphosa used tactics such as cabinet re-shuffling to advance patronage politics and to weaken potential political contenders. A strategy that is proven to stabilize regimes and increases the risk of rebellion (30). These leader adopt these catchy political survival strategies without being aware they are colonial seeds to sow divisions, conflicts and sabotage of any progressive cause they try to lead.

Colonial Language Command for Political Pilotage

English being a “world” language is a testament to the extent of British colonisation footprint compared to other European colonizers. English is not only a language for communication, but constant monument of the UK as a defeater and everyone else as conquered. One may argue english is unifying the world. The critics would ask as to who’s benefit is the world unified. The liberals would say, everyone who is prepared to learn the rules and follow them will benefit. However, the concern is when rules create conflicts- then everyone must participate in crafting the rules. Given there are Second Language English classrooms from formerly colonized countries (India, Sri Lanka, Pakistan, Bangladesh, Nigeria, South Africa, and Zimbabwe, etc.) that are systemically excluded from even the knowledge of which rules help on what (29). All they know is conflict among each other. Because some among them are paid to ensure conflict is the order of the day within their under-resource communities. In such cases english language, not only does it create schism, but it serves as a hugger-mugger systematic deprivation of access to quality teaching and learning, mainstream economy participation, access to Rule of Law and Historical Justice Litigation.

English is leveraged by most African politicians to ascend to position of power. In fact politicians proudly rely on ‘divide-and-rule’ political strategies to pilotage and to survive in high offices. For example, strategies relied upon to break up rival concentrations of power into pieces are the very same strategies that destroyed customs and heritage. For example, the same way the coloniser chopped and changed traditional leaderships, they shuffle and reshuffle cabinet as though its a ‘way of life’. Also ensuring no one must politically account for failures of every department.

In worse cases, those in charge will accumulate many portfolios under themselves. This most done only just to hand those portfolios over to someone else in the next reshuffle. While they do so to keep their opponents weak but they also intensify

the collective grouping for potential rebellion. These strategies are perfected and trusted by colonisers to ensure conflicts are the order of the day. This is another way coloniser sponsor counter-revolution traditions to “left revolutionary organisations”. They personalise these strategies and tactics to naturally brew internal divisions, factions and conflicts. They preside over politics that are constantly preoccupied with discussing people and events- and devoid of empowering each other with anything of substance. That is to ensure a spring of source of conflicts. To them the more name dropping and the more they remember events is the reflection of their political strength.

Leadership that dependent on strategies and tactics of the coloniser for internal political navigation only render their organisations “liberal”- even if they profess to be left or extreme left. Colonial power tags organisation as neutralised passive allies. To maintain dominance, colonisers gauge their elasticity coefficient by triggering internal conflicts through their subjugated proxies- from time to time. What is even worse is that these proxies are not even aware they are proxies. Coloniser will build a model based of their strategies and tactics that simulate what should be happening when their strategies in full-swing. Then create bogus sources and leaks to exaggerate internal conflicts and mistrust.

What is worse is that colonisers are now grooming them early child development stages. They use modern digital games that are often embed with colonial narratives, perpetuating stereotypes of non-Western cultures as “primitive” or “inferior.” This digital divide-and-rule reinforces hierarchical worldviews, shaping how players perceive and classify different cultures (31). In fact, from a young age, they are socialised through modern digital games they are developed affinity to colonial culture. They perceive such game features as supplementary, complimentary or subordinate to their ordinary /serious/ everyday/ real world strategies and tactics for their personal development. Taking note that these colonial games are based upon establishing a singular hierarchical world order which involves discovery, assessment and classification of other world (views) as primitive, inferior, irrational and infantile

and hence open to subjugation, exploitation, dispossession and elimination. In this scheme, the question as to whether a world is divided or undivided (between real and play), functions as a criterion to judge and classify cultures as civilized or primitive (31).

Institutionalized Communal Divisions

“Communalizing Colonial Policies” (CCPs) are mechanisms design to augment institutionalized ethnic, religious, and social divisions to create lasting societal fragmentation. Research shows that political exclusion—especially of certain ethnic groups—remains a significant predictor of ethnic conflict in multiethnic, postcolonial states (32, 33, 34).

Account for Natural Conflicts

It is fair to acknowledge that conflicts are natural, to be expected and can not be avoided. They arise from the fact that people will always act in a manner that demonstrate competing interests. Not withstanding that society is a complex network of social relationships. and as such human conflicts are even more inevitable. Marie Doucey point out that there are sometimes protracted conflicts. Failure to identify root causes of protracted conflicts is responsible for uninterrupted violence and irreparable societies (37). Creating a need for conflicts to be resolved, and resolved wisely. Settlement of conflicts is necessary for societal harmony, peace, amity and sustainable development. As such effective conflict resolution is a necessity for the survival of any civilization. History teach us that Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) were integral-part of various civilizations. It safe to suggest they have proven to be historically preferred alternative to prevent the cost of physical combat. Even though is recently they are understood as preferred alternative to litigation.

Engineering of Artificial Conflicts

Between peace and conflict is always either need for survival and self-actualisation. This proposition arise from 1943 Psychologist- Mr. Abraham Harold Maslow who suggested his Theory of Human Motivation. He postulates that human motivation can be illustrated through a hierarchy of needs. That is often portrayed in the shape of a pyramid with the largest, most fundamental needs at the bottom. And the need for self-actualization transcend at the top of the pyramid. At the bottom, these needs include food, shelter, clothing, rest, air, water, sleep and sexual satisfaction. They basic human needs (also called biological needs), hence they lie at the lowest level in the hierarchy of needs. In fact, they have a priority over all other needs to almost all biological species. These needs cannot be postponed for long. Unless and until these basic physiological needs are satisfied to the required extent, other needs do not motivate human behaviour. A hungry person, for example, is just not in a position to think of anything else except his hunger or food. According to Maslow, 'man lives by bread alone,' when there is no bread - (38). Those at the apex of the hierarchy have graduated from being motivated needs. Instead they are aware that they need the people from their level of hierarchy for attainment of their self-actualisation. This creates inter-dependance, that compels a relationship to be defined. The relations can either be mutual, economical or parasitic (or predatory).

The nature of such relationship would depend on the set of ideals of ideology that must inform the energy/resources to build such relations. Tosaka Jun argue that ideology is not just a set of ideas imposed from above. Ideologies are deeply embedded in the routines, practices, and cultural symbols that shape daily life. In his reasoning, he advocated for a more materialist, praxis-oriented approach to philosophy in order to formulate ideals that engage with the realities of fascism and militarism in Japan (39). In that regard Enrique Dussel's thesis, "I conquer, therefore I am" (*ego conquiro*) underscores the epistemological foundation of colonial ambition (25). The Dussel's thesis suggests colonial behaviour turn to be motivated by the desire for self-actualisation. Defining the relationships between those on top and those at the bottom of the matriarchy as predatory (parasitic). Given that Self actualisation in definition is the desire to become what one is capable of becoming.

It is a never ending need for 'growth'. A coloniser must conquer if they wish to improve or grow their economy. This involves utilising all their potentials to the maximum their extent and desire to become what of capable of becoming. Though every country is capable of self-actualization, many do not reach this stage of ambitions. To fully satisfy this need requires an attitude of a very hungry predator.

Predatory and Parasitic Principles (Triple-P)

The willingness and ability to deceive others for selfish gain is an ever-growing problem in the modern world. This is common with respect to financial behaviour. Predatory and parasitic financial behaviours threaten cooperative communities worldwide. There are also similar patterns of deception across long- versus short-term behaviours in parasitic micro-organisms as well as predatory nonhuman mimics and humans. For example, a nonhuman animal mimic is defined as an organism that, through various means of deception (e.g., behavioural, visual, and chemical), appears to possess certain characteristics but actually possesses different characteristics. A predatory mimic (or Mertensian mimic) is a nonhuman animal that uses such confusion for hunting prey. A common example is the evolved similarity among the coral snake and two other snakes: the king snake and the milk snake. Despite their similar appearance, the coral snake is venomous, whereas the milk snake and the king snake are not. However, the confusion among these types of snakes benefits all of them. Similarly, infection-producing, parasitic micro-organisms use deception to gain an evolutionary advantage. For example, the human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) confuses a host's immune system by hiding within naturally occurring cells (41).

Colonial Strategies and Tactics

Predatory and parasitic deceptive behaviours are not limited to nonhuman animals and micro-organisms; they are also pervasive in modern human society. Parasitic and predatory human political deception spans from simple and immediate forms of to elaborate and long-term colonial divide and conquer. Colonial divide and conquer are the following strategy and tactics. 1) Augment and create differences within

conquered population. 2) Channel and exploit the differences to benefit the power of the coloniser. 3) They politicize differences to carry them over into the post-colonial period. 4) Identifying, find or groom hostile population. Create a physical environment for hostile groups to interact (through prisons, squatter camps, townships, hostels, flats etc.). The fuel and spark conflict among hostile groups. 5) Facilitate immigration from one colonial territory to another. 6) Support religious conversion as a means to inculcate convenient western values to control belief system. 8) Use education to augment one colonial group with relatively higher level of education against the population with lower education level. 9) Use selective recruitment to arm forces and policing. The use selective recruitment mechanism of less educated. Use less educated to humble the educated. 10) provide polarising ideologies to ensure their political efforts are self-modulating.

Performance-Evaluative Scan of Colonial Strategy and Tactics

Last year Daniel N. Mlambo and Mandla A. Mubecu's published testaments of effectiveness of colonial predatory-parasitic tactics. They demonstrate that all African countries have adopted democratic systems on their governance. Their observation is line to Fukuyama who posited the "end of history". The universalisation of Western liberal democracy as the final form of human government. Western liberal democracy has now been adopted by former colonies. Mlambo et. al. point out that nothing has changed. The post-colonial leader still rely to the same tactics of colonialism to maintain control, force, tyranny and oppression (42).

Modification and Modernisation of Colonialism

Perhaps, it is important to re-visit the fact that slavery and colonization were found to be bone of contention among ambitious kingdoms and countries. The contests were found to the reasons behind conflicts and destruction of Europe. Colonisation needed to be modernized. The modernization meant the need to modify colonisation to ensure primarily sustainable development of Europe and secondary its colonies. This informed the founding principles of international organisations such as UN, IMF, WB, WHO etc. This translated to what Mlambo et al remarks as colonialism that has

simply transformed from offensive domination to clandestine power manipulation of colonies.

“The Great Trek”

In 1652 Dutch colonised the Cape of South Africa. In 1795 British took-over the coloniser of South Africa. The Boers, which were descendants of Dutch settlers in South Africa, took several decades to establish their two homelands which were the Orange Free State and the Transvaal. Which was characterised as the Great Trek and occurred in the 1830s. By the 1850s, they had founded these independent Boer homelands in the interior regions of South Africa. British had them conditional autonomy from British. On these homelands, British afforded them an opportunity to learn to govern in a manner that is accepted by Britain. The benefit was that they opportunity to govern their own affairs according to their beliefs.

In land Mineral and their Impact

The challenge began when they discovered diamonds in the 1860s in the region of Kimberley (bordering the Orange Free State and Cape Colony). This led to British annexed the Transvaal in 1877, which led to tensions that escalated into the First Anglo-Boer War in 1880. And subsequently the Boers that were resentful of British interference in their Homelands. They resisted and ultimately “forced” Britain to recognize the independence of the Transvaal once again after a series of the Boer victories. The Pretoria Convention (in 1881) and London Convention (in 1884) reestablished Transvaal’s autonomy. But British oversight on foreign affairs of these homelands was a clear condition of the autonomy.

Again in 1886, the Boers discovered gold in the Transvaal. This dramatically increased British interest in these areas. In 1899, the Second Anglo-Boer War broke out. This brutal conflict involved scorched-earth tactics by the British. The use of concentration camps for Boer civilians, and significant loss of life. The war ended in 1902 with the Treaty of Vereeniging, which marked the dissolution of both Boer republics and their absorption into the British Empire.

British Fixation to Sustainability of their Authority

It is important to note the pattern of British, that whenever they wrote history- they always present themselves as victims of defeat. This pattern demonstrate that British has long identified the difference between power and authority. Their colonial style was the improvement of historical fallen empires. Their approach has always be to lease power and own authority. This history of South African colonisation demonstrate that for more than a century Boers will enjoy leasing power- while authority remained with the British.

Colonial Consolidation of both Power and Authority

On the befit of hindsight, beginning of the 20th century the Boer had accumulated seven decades of self government under supervision of the British. They must have proven that they could be entrusted with the entire British Colony. Despite few conflicts- British optimised the lease as a strategy to channel native colonial resentment to the Boer. Write a new history of British Colony. The new history was to be written as Apartheid History. The Boers were to be forced to mentor the Native, to prepare them for their turn to enjoy a century lease of power. This plan need British to consolidate both its power and its authority.

As the war ended in 1902 with the Treaty of Vereeniging, which marked the dissolution of both Boer republics and their absorption into the British Empire. Under the terms of the treaty, the Orange Free State and Transvaal became British colonies, with certain protections for Boer culture and language but under British control. The dissolution led to both territories governed as British colonies until the formation of the Union of South Africa in 1910.

British gave Boer 100 Years Power Lease

1910 marked the burial of all colonial gruesome history. This was the opportunity for British to transform its combat colonisation strategy into a cohesion strategy. This

was an era when in their neighbourhood the steel industrial revolution was booming. Countries were using their economic fruits to increase their military capacity. Germany in particular was not only consolidating its military capacity but also solidify alliances. UK during this era, had to cut down financial expenditure from its foreign policy. Its leaning strategy was to lease out the power of the colony to Dutch descendents. This must have been very convenient under the circumstances.

The new union that was created by merging the Cape Colony, Natal, Transvaal, and Orange River Colony, gave limited self-governance to South Africans but remained official part of the British Empire.

De Ja Vu of Democratic Republic of South Africa

The this point going forward, patterns for South African power dynamics clearly pronounced. Reflecting on the current Democratic dispensation (1994 – 2024), provides practical meaning to "de ja vu phrase". Studying this history carefully only can you crystallise your appreciation of current affairs. This work is confident to claim that it provides understanding that can help you simulate the near to the distant future.

Then Union of South Africa was led initially by Louis Botha (1910 to 1919) and subsequently Jan Smuts (1919 to 1924). Both Prime Ministers were former Boer generals who became allies of the British. They headed the South African Party (SAP) that supported cooperation with British authorities and economic modernization. While Botha and Smuts supported British policies (including joining World War I on the side of Britain), they faced opposition from other Afrikaners who harboured resentment from the Anglo-Boer Wars. Many Afrikaners opposed British influence, seeing it as an attempt to undermine their culture and identity.

In 1914, Afrikaners who were disillusioned with Botha and Smuts' pro-British policies formed the National Party (NP) under J.B.M. Hertzog. The NP aimed to protect Afrikaner interests, promote Afrikaans culture, and reduce British dominance.

Replaced Dutch as second official language by Afrikaans in 1925. Instituted a new national flag in 1928. Approved women's suffrage for white women (meant white women right to vote) with the Women's Enfranchisement Act, 1930 (entrenched the for white women of age 21 and above to vote and run for office). Adoption of the Statute of Westminster 1931 (Westminster 1931 is an act of the Parliament of the United Kingdom that sets the basis for the relationship between the Dominions, now called Commonwealth realms, and the Crown).

Hertzog removed Black voters from the common voters roll. Created coalition with South African Party to form the United Party. In 1924, Hertzog's NP won the general election and formed a coalition government, marking the beginning of a government focused on Afrikaner interests.

Hertzog's NP era marked the transition from combat to covert domination of British rule in South Africa through Statute of Westminster 1931. In metamorphic terms the British Statute of Westminster 1931 as part of South African acts transformed predatory UK style of authority to parasitic mimicking style of authority. Resigned after the United Party caucus refused to accept his stance of neutrality in World War II in 1939.

COLONISATION TRANSFORMATION FROM PREDATORY TO INFECTIOUS PARASITIC AUTHORITY

RATE OF REGIONAL COLONISATION TRANSFORMING FROM OFFENSIVE TO COVRT

In 1924, Smuts' South African Party (SAP) lost the election, primarily due to growing Afrikaner resentment over his policies, particularly his pro-British stance and perceived neglect of Afrikaner economic and cultural interests. The National Party, led by Hertzog, capitalized on Afrikaner nationalism and formed a coalition government with the Labour Party, known as the *Pact Government*. Smuts remained an active leader of the opposition and criticized Hertzog's policies, including his economic strategies and efforts to promote Afrikaner interests over unity within the South African population.

He opposed the growing isolationist policies of the Pact Government, particularly Hertzog's attempts to limit South Africa's ties to the British Commonwealth. During his years in opposition, Smuts became more deeply involved in global intellectual and philosophical debates. He wrote extensively on his concept of *Holism*, which emphasized the interconnectedness of the universe. This work influenced fields ranging from ecology to governance. Economic hardships during the Great Depression created dissatisfaction with Hertzog's government. This economic crisis led Hertzog to form a coalition with Smuts' South African Party. Together, they merged their parties to form the United Party (UP) in 1934, with the goal of unifying South Africans and addressing economic challenges. Hertzog remained Prime Minister, while Smuts served as his deputy and Minister of Justice. The coalition aimed to reconcile differences between the Afrikaner nationalists and the English-speaking South Africans. Smuts played a key role in promoting policies that balanced Afrikaner interests with South Africa's ties to Britain.

He supported industrial and agricultural development policies to stabilize the South African economy during the global depression. By the late 1930s, tensions grew within the United Party. Hertzog advocated for neutrality in the looming global conflict (World War II), reflecting Afrikaner nationalist sentiment. Smuts, however, firmly supported South Africa's alignment with Britain, recognizing the importance of the Commonwealth and the threat posed by Nazi Germany. When World War II

broke out in 1939, Hertzog insisted that South Africa remain neutral, but Smuts argued for entering the war on the side of the Allies. This disagreement led to a parliamentary vote, where Smuts narrowly won the support of the United Party caucus.

Hertzog resigned as Prime Minister, and Smuts succeeded him in 1939. Smuts' victory reflected his ability to rally English-speaking South Africans and moderate Afrikaners who recognized the strategic importance of supporting Britain in the war. His long-standing reputation as an international statesman and his contributions during World War I bolstered his credibility as a wartime leader.

Upon taking office, Smuts immediately committed South Africa to the Allied cause in World War II. The dominance of the US dollar post-Bretton Woods (1944) established a framework where global financial aid operated through dollar-pegged transactions. The end of World War 2 was declared in 1945. Post World War 2 in 1945, Smuts was instrumental in shaping the preamble to the United Nations Charter. His contribution reflected his commitment to a vision of global cooperation and collective security, which he saw as a lesson from both World Wars. The UN, in Smuts' view, was a mechanism to prevent future global conflicts by fostering dialogue and mutual understanding among nations.

After World War II, the global focus shifted toward human rights, with the UN playing a central role. Indigenous rights became part of the broader discourse on decolonization and self-determination, influenced by the atrocities of the war and the principles of equality enshrined in the UN Charter.

The Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948), influenced by the UN Charter, began addressing the systemic inequalities faced by Indigenous peoples under

colonial rule. However, these discussions were often sidelined by the geopolitical realities of maintaining empire structures. Smuts' remained among those who resisted to apply the principles of equality and self-determination to Indigenous South Africans. His policies continued to enforce segregation and economic exploitation, reflecting the contradiction between his international advocacy for peace and his domestic policies of racial inequality.

Smuts, as an "imperialist at heart", sought to bolster the Commonwealth but faced a global order increasingly critical of colonialism. Given his close relationship with Britain- critics viewed him as a staunch supporter of the British Empire. His domestic policies were in line his view of colonization as a civilizing mission, consistent with the colonial ideologies of his time- today consistent with Helen Zille political position. This perspective clashed with the post-war momentum toward decolonization, driven by anti-imperial sentiments that emerged from nations in Asia and Africa. The atrocities of World War II, particularly the Holocaust, forced a global reckoning with systemic racism and oppression. This moral awakening influenced the UN's human rights agenda, placing Indigenous rights and decolonization in sharper focus. His era exemplifies the transition from imperial dominance to a world order increasingly shaped by "self-determination and equality" (50). The geopolitical shifts following World War II, as noted by Hughes (1988), revealed the vulnerabilities of imperial powers like Britain. This decline in imperial dominance, combined with growing nationalist movements, forced a reevaluation of colonization within global institutions like the UN. The UN, influenced by its charter's principles, became a platform for challenging colonial rule, even as leaders like Smuts sought to maintain imperial ties. As Hughes highlights, Britain's ability to defend its empire was in decline even before World War II, as domestic politics raised questions about its capacity to maintain colonial dominance.

Afrikaner Were Misled

In 1948, the National Party, led by D.F. Malan, won a decisive victory in the general election. This victory marked the start of "apartheid". A decoy enabled to erase British colonial history and to camouflage colonial authority of UK over South Africa. It was during this period that British unleashed its divide and rule and constant conflict inducement. Britain used its authority to influence NP to implement apartheid laws to institutionalize racial segregation and protect white dominance (under the guise of protecting Afrikaner). Afrikaner leaders in the National Party thought apartheid was a way to safeguard South Africa from British influence and protect Afrikaner identity. British allowed NP government to promote Afrikaner culture, language, and nationalism, favouring Afrikaner business interests over British ones. Key laws included the Population Registration Act, Group Areas Act, and Pass Laws, all of which restricted the rights and freedoms of nonwhite South Africans.

Republic of South Africa- Ushering for Democratic Republic of South Africa

In 1961, under the leadership of Prime Minister Hendrik Verwoerd, South Africa became a republic following a whites-only referendum. The establishment of the Republic of South Africa appeared as formally severed ties with the British monarchy. It appeared as removal of the Queen Elizabeth II as head of state and withdrawal from the Commonwealth. As a republic, South Africa was now presented as fully under Afrikaner control. National Party truly thought it was in charge. It diligently enforced apartheid policies that deeply affected social, political, and economic life. The NP was now allowed to establish Afrikaner control over all major state institutions, including the judiciary, police, and military. The British used black South Africans to defect black colonisation towards apartheid regime. The apartheid regime faced increasing international condemnation, sanctions, and isolation. It was during

this era the Afrikaner government promoted Afrikaner cultural organizations, like the Broederbond (a secretive Afrikaner organization that influenced key institutions) and expanded Afrikaans language use in education, media, and government. Afrikaner business and cultural networks flourished, consolidating power among the Afrikaner elite.

Democratic Republic of South Africa

South Africa's reintegration into global markets after 1994 occurred when US dollar's primacy was already at the centre of IMF and World Bank terms for Post-Conflicts Reconstruction. World Bank advocated privatization and fiscal reforms to attract foreign direct investment. While IMF was providing policy advice that was emphasizing macroeconomic stability. Credit Ratings Agencies critical for shaping foreign capital flows.

At this point in 1994, South Africa was drowning in debt. Needed a lot of advice and support from international organisations such as Credit Rating Agencies, IMF, USAID, World Bank etc. Prior governing experience was a challenge. Despite the effort to buffer it with Government of National Unit (GNU). The GNU was led by president Nelson Mandela with two deputy presidents FW De Klerk and Thabo Mbeki. That GNU was confronted by the fact that there were no funds to fulfil the promises made to the public. Government had to rely on the support of international organisations for fulfilment of public promises. The primary condition was that the government had to relinquish control of strategic infrastructure development, transferring this responsibility to the private sector. To ensure capacity and expertise, the government was required to prioritize internationally connected private sectors, which were branded as "international investors." To formalize commitments from both international aid providers and the South African government, a memorandum of understanding (MoU) was developed, known as GEAR (Growth, Employment, and Redistribution) to fund the RDP project. GEAR functioned as a neoliberal policy, with its core mechanisms being Black Economic Empowerment (BEE) and a tender system. These mechanisms aimed to integrate black South Africans into the RDP.

GEAR was adopted, and the economy grew at a rate of 6%. Fiscal resources were allocated to increase access to tertiary education, basic services, and job creation. Investments in higher education produced a pool of educated individuals, many of whom entered BEE entrepreneurship. As more South Africans benefited from basic services and the growing BEE program, support for neoliberal policies increased. Over the next 30 years, white-owned companies maintained a presence in the tendering system but focused their entrepreneurial efforts in sectors such as retail, finance, law, mining, agriculture, fishing, manufacturing, education, and health. Meanwhile, the growth of the middle class led to a wider gap between the middle and lower classes. Populist politicians began to exploit this gap, generating political rhetoric that fuelled resentment between the black middle class and lower class. They labeled the poor as "revolutionaries" and the middle class as "neoliberal sellouts."

Today, this divide is exacerbated by the beneficiaries of colonial-era structures, who use international aid distributed through the UN to white-owned NGOs, purportedly for projects in alternative dispute resolution, justice access, private investigation, and media. Some of these NGOs leverage rogue intelligence operations to widen the gap between the two black classes.

The consequences of this internal division are severe: escalating black-on-black violent crime, high reoffending rates, overcrowded correctional centers, an under-resourced judiciary, collapsing families, rampant substance abuse, fragile generational wealth security, and more. Living conditions for indigenous people are arguably worse than before democracy, with murder rates, crime statistics, and correctional center populations far higher than before. Judicial backlogs have increased, family units are more dysfunctional, and substance abuse issues are escalating. Despite economic exclusion during apartheid, upward social mobility was more stable than it is today. Ultimately, the RDP has only resulted in unreasonable inflation, and trust—an essential component of societal stability—has been eroded.

A solution requires more than unity; it demands a rebuilding of trust. Trust, however, has been profoundly damaged. To address this, the upper class must help fund an RDP of trust—a project of reconstruction that will require deep, ongoing mediation. African problems will require African mediators who understand these issues at a fundamental level. As black South Africans, we must recognize that our identity as Africans precedes socioeconomic divisions of wealth or poverty.

Africans are family. The legacy of colonialism has divided us, eroding trust between communities. Just as families subjected to domestic violence experience a deterioration of trust, so too has our collective experience eroded trust. But with determined effort, trust can be rebuilt. The current struggle between classes is akin to domestic conflict, one that can be resolved amicably if the principles of mediation are carefully followed.

Effective mediation requires voluntary engagement from both classes, a commitment to uncovering and addressing the root causes of distrust. Both sides must be prepared to negotiate and find common ground.

The mediation process must also acknowledge that there are both victims and perpetrators in this class conflict. If Africans do not rebuild trust among each other, we risk being forever unable to challenge colonial systems and claim true freedom. Scandinavia, for example, has built its societies on a foundation of mutual trust; a similar path could hold the key to sustainable unity and prosperity for Africa.

Systematic Colonial Targeting Health of Indigenous South African

Public Health Act of 1919

This act institutionalized racial discrimination within healthcare services. It established separate health services for different racial groups, directing resources and medical personnel to “European” facilities. Isolated underfunded healthcare for Indigenous communities. Consequently, Indigenous Peoples had limited access to

quality medical care. Designed to create higher rates of preventable diseases and fatalities Indigenous communities. The act reinforced a system that conveyed racial inferiority. Targeted mental health by fostering feelings of inferiority, exclusion and marginalization.

Urban Areas Act of 1923

This act created racially segregated urban areas, forcing Indigenous Peoples into overcrowded, poorly serviced "locations" far from urban economic centers. These areas were characterized by inadequate sanitation, insufficient water supply, and limited healthcare access. Designed to justify increased infectious diseases diagnoses and fatality. The enforced relocation and confinement resulted in psychological stress, anxiety, a deepened sense of disenfranchisement, terror and isolation. Isolated to orchestrate immune disorder and malnutrition.

Natives (Urban Areas) Consolidation Act of 1945

This act formalized "pass laws" and restrictions on Indigenous populations' movement into urban centers. This legislation severely limited Indigenous Peoples' ability to seek employment and live in areas with better health facilities. It trapped them in poverty-stricken and under-resourced areas with limited access to healthcare. The law's restrictive nature generated a climate of fear and frustration, negatively affecting the mental health. Forced to endure dehumanizing restrictions on their freedom and autonomy.

Population Registration Act of 1950

In 1950 colonial government populated an act called Population Registration Act of 1950. I would imagine because of affirmative and BEE this act should still be valid- The act primary purpose was classification of SA population. It made mandatory racial categorization. Aimed to foster a rigid social hierarchy that psychologically traumatised Indigenous People. Every time they had to devalue their identity and heritage- in a manner that was designed to demean it. Individuals and families were

often forced to confront state-imposed identities that disrupted personal and cultural ties, which intensified mental health struggles related to identity and self-worth.

Group Areas Act of 1950

By segregating residential areas based on race, this act forced Indigenous Peoples into overcrowded, unsanitary areas far from essential health services. The poor living conditions in designated "non-European" areas led to numerous health issues, including malnutrition, respiratory illnesses, and other communicable diseases exacerbated by a lack of medical resources. The Act's restrictions created a pervasive sense of confinement, isolation, and helplessness, fostering chronic mental health issues within Indigenous communities as a result of enforced socioeconomic and spatial marginalization.

Separate Amenities Act of 1953

This act formalized the segregation of public facilities, including hospitals, clinics, and recreational spaces. Indigenous communities were relegated to substandard healthcare facilities, which were often understaffed and under-resourced compared to "white-only" hospitals and clinics. This lack of access to quality healthcare facilities contributed to higher morbidity and mortality rates among Indigenous populations. The explicit segregation of public amenities compounded feelings of inferiority and societal rejection, contributing to widespread mental health issues related to stress, anxiety, and internalized stigma among Indigenous people.

Bantu Education Act of 1953

While focused on education, the Bantu Education Act promoted a racially inferior curriculum for Indigenous students, which restricted access to knowledge on health, hygiene, and well-being. By limiting educational content to vocational skills, the Act contributed indirectly to poor health outcomes by depriving Indigenous people of essential health literacy, a key factor in preventive care.

Separate Amenities Amendment Act of 1960

This act intensified the enforcement of the Separate Amenities Act by expanding the types of segregated services, further limiting Indigenous Peoples' access to quality healthcare. Indigenous people were often forced to travel long distances to reach clinics that were poorly equipped and inadequately staffed. The act's reinforcement of segregation instilled a sense of hopelessness and disenfranchisement within Indigenous communities, fostering mental health struggles associated with systemic exclusion and marginalization.

Mental Disorders Act of 1967

This act applied a Eurocentric view of mental health that often mischaracterized Indigenous cultural practices as signs of mental disorder. Indigenous individuals could be institutionalized for behavior that diverged from Western norms, leading to a lack of culturally appropriate mental health support and an erosion of Indigenous spiritual and cultural practices. The misdiagnosis and mistreatment of Indigenous people within mental health institutions led to substandard care, abuse, and neglect in treatment facilities. Indigenous individuals were also isolated from their communities, exacerbating both physical and mental health declines.

Prohibition of Mixed Marriages Act of 1949 and Immorality Act of 1950

These acts not only restricted interracial relationships but also deeply impacted Indigenous individuals' mental well-being. Families were divided based on race classifications, and individuals suffered from social ostracization, contributing to mental health issues such as depression, identity crises, and social anxiety. The social pressures and legal restrictions imposed on personal relationships fostered an environment of secrecy and stress, affecting physical health through stress-related illnesses and reducing access to social support systems crucial for overall well-being.

Colonial Systematic Targeting Social Stability of Indigenous South African

Natives Land Act of 1913

This Act restricted black people ownership of land to specific areas, amounting to just 7% of South Africa's land. Enforced dispossessing Indigenous communities of their traditional lands. The Act disrupted longstanding social structures rooted in land-based communities and cultural practices. The loss of land led to forced relocations. Broke apart communities, extended families, and social networks. Indigenous social stability, traditionally tied to the land, was severely undermined. Families were forced into overcrowded "reserves" or migrant labor camps.

Urban Areas Act of 1923

This Act laid the groundwork for racial segregation within urban spaces, dictating where Indigenous individuals could live, work, and move. Indigenous populations were pushed into separate, under-resourced urban areas (later called "townships") far from city centers where jobs and better services were available. By isolating Indigenous workers from their families and traditional communities, the Act weakened social bonds and disrupted traditional support systems. The spatial isolation of communities limited social interaction between families, altering community dynamics and weakening group identity.

Native Administration Act of 1927

This Act centralized control over Indigenous affairs, granting the government authority over the administration of Indigenous peoples' lives, including marriage, inheritance, and tribal governance. Traditional leaders were often replaced or co-opted by colonial-appointed officials. This law promoted sidelining of traditional authorities. It was designed to erode Indigenous governance systems. To destabilize established social structures. Reducing the role of family elders and community leaders in decision-making processes. The act shifted authority away from family-based structures to state-controlled systems. Thereby eroded family autonomy.

Population Registration Act of 1950

This act mandated the racial classification of all South Africans, enforcing a rigid social hierarchy based on race. Families were often split if members were classified differently, and communities were divided according to arbitrary racial lines. This Act's classifications sometimes split families into different racial categories, effectively tearing families apart. The psychological stress and social instability created by forced categorization destabilized family and community cohesion, leading to a fracturing of traditional social bonds.

Group Areas Act of 1950

This Act designated specific urban and rural areas for different racial groups, which led to the forced relocation of Indigenous communities. Families were forcibly removed from multi-generational homes and relocated to areas with poor infrastructure and limited resources. Uprooted entire communities. Used this Act to disrupt social cohesion, fractured community identity. People's support networks was systematically broken down. Families and communities were fragmented. Deliberately increased isolation and loss of social structure stability. Families were forced to adapt to unfamiliar surroundings away from ancestral land and cultural heritage sites.

Bantu Authorities Act of 1951

This Act established "Bantu Authorities" in rural areas as a means to administer Indigenous communities under state-controlled "tribal" governance structures. It removed power from traditional leaders and replaced them with government-appointed chiefs, often leading to tensions and conflict within communities. The imposed state-selected authorities compromised the legitimacy of community leadership, creating divisions and weakened Indigenous governance systems. This destabilised fostered intra-community conflicts resolution mechanisms and weakened trust on community leadership and undermined Indigenous social stability.

Separate Representation of Voters Act of 1951

This Act removed voting rights from the Cape's mixed-race population (the "Coloured" population), further entrenched racial divisions within the political sphere and excluded Indigenous voices from civic participation. The systematic exclusion of Indigenous voices from political processes fostered feelings of disenfranchisement and social marginalization. Indigenous communities lost representation semblance. This exclusionary policy weakened the overall social structure and undermined community agency and influence over local and national affairs.

The Promotion of Bantu Self-Government Act of 1959

This Act created separate "Bantustans" (or homelands) for various Indigenous ethnic groups, formalizing a policy of ethnic division and fragmentation. Each Bantustan was meant to be self-governing but was financially dependent on the apartheid state, severely limiting its autonomy. By creating ethnic homelands, this Act institutionalized ethnic divisions within Indigenous communities, effectively fracturing broader Indigenous identity into smaller, often rival groups. This division fostered inter-group tensions and undermined unity, making collective social organization more challenging and fostering distrust among Indigenous groups.

Reservation of Separate Amenities Act of 1953

This law enforced racial segregation in public amenities such as parks, transportation, and recreation facilities, relegating Indigenous people to inferior services and restricted access areas. The enforced separation in everyday spaces further divided communities and reduced social interaction among different racial groups. Indigenous people were systematically excluded from areas that provided better services, embedding social hierarchies and creating structural inequalities that limited inter-communal relationships and solidarity.

Prohibition of Mixed Marriages Act of 1949 and Immorality Act of 1950

These laws prohibited marriages and relationships between Europeans and non-Europeans, making interracial relationships illegal. This restriction on personal

relationships reinforced rigid racial divisions. Criminalized interracial relationships and impacted social stability of families with mixed heritage. Families and communities with interracial ties faced legal persecution and social ostracization. Increased isolation and fractured familial and community bonds.

Extension of University Education Act of 1959

This act prohibited non-European students from attending universities reserved for Europeans, forcing them into racially segregated institutions. This restriction stifled social mobility for Indigenous students and reinforced educational inequality. The exclusion from premier universities limited career advancement and economic stability for Indigenous students and entrenched social stratification. Denied equal educational opportunities and perpetuated systemic marginalization of Indigenous communities. This act is responsible for current black community and family instability.

Colonial Systematic Targeting Spirituality of Indigenous South African

This analysis is based on legislation highlighting how colonial laws were strategically designed to suppress Indigenous spirituality, undermined cultural beliefs, and impose European religious and ideological dominance.

Native Administration Act of 1927

This Act granted the government extensive control over Indigenous affairs, including religious practices. Indigenous leaders who held significant spiritual authority, were often replaced by government-appointed officials. The replacement of traditional authorities weakened the influence of Indigenous spiritual leaders, marginalized traditional religious practitioners. The government's power over Indigenous lands allowed them to restrict access to sites of spiritual importance. Sacred locations that held cultural and religious significance were either repurposed or prohibited for Indigenous worship, undermining spiritual practices tied to the land.

Bantu Education Act of 1953

This Act enforced a racially segregated and inferior education system for Indigenous communities. The curriculum omitted Indigenous histories, spiritual imperatives of languages. Christian teachings and European cultural values dominated the curriculum. The aim was to erode traditional spiritual identities and instill European religious beliefs. The exclusion of Indigenous spiritual narratives from educational content, intentionally devalued Indigenous religious beliefs and traditions. Students were often discouraged from practicing or even acknowledging their spiritual heritage, creating a generational disconnect from Indigenous spirituality.

Suppression of Communism Act of 1950

This law, while ostensibly targeting communism, was often used to suppress any opposition to colonial system. Indigenous spiritual leaders who promoted cultural resilience were suppressed. Spiritual leaders who advocated for Indigenous autonomy or resisted cultural assimilation were branded as subversives and were

frequently silenced, exiled, or imprisoned. Spiritual gatherings or teachings that were perceived as anti-colonial were suppressed under this Act. Traditional religious gatherings, particularly those advocating unity or resistance, were banned, further restricting Indigenous spiritual expression.

Church and State Collaboration through Missionary Education

The government encouraged missionary activity among Indigenous communities. Missionary schools introduced Christianity as the primary spiritual framework. Often dismissed or actively condemned Indigenous spiritual practices as “pagan” or “heathen.” That educational system aimed to convert Indigenous populations to Christianity and systematically eroded Indigenous belief systems. Christian missionaries often prohibited Indigenous spiritual practices within their institutions. They replaced traditional ceremonies, rituals, and rites of passage with Christian alternatives. This led to a significant decline in Indigenous spiritual observances and disrupted the continuity of cultural and spiritual traditions.

The Witchcraft Suppression Act of 1957

The Act targeted Indigenous healers, spiritual leaders, and traditional practices by labeling them as “witchcraft.” Practices such as divination, healing, and other Indigenous rituals were criminalized, effectively outlawed significant elements of Indigenous spiritual life. Branded traditional healers and religious leaders as criminals. This legislation alienated Indigenous spiritual authorities and stigmatized traditional healing practices. Indigenous communities that relied on these spiritual leaders for guidance and support, faced increased marginalization of their cultural identities and practices.

Extension of University Education Act of 1959

This Act restricted Indigenous access to mainstream universities. It created segregated institutions where the curriculum reflected European ideologies and Christian doctrine. Further distanced Indigenous students from their spiritual heritage. Students from Indigenous communities were cut off from their cultural and

spiritual heritage. This created a gap in spiritual knowledge and understanding for educated Indigenous individuals, limiting their capacity to serve as spiritual leaders in their communities.

The Promotion of Bantu Self-Government Act of 1959

This Act designated separate “homelands” based on ethnic divisions, fragmenting Indigenous communities and diluting unified spiritual practices. By isolating ethnic groups within confined areas, the government disrupted shared cultural practices and weakened the collective spiritual identity that unified Indigenous people. The government often appointed chiefs or officials aligned with state ideologies, replacing legitimate spiritual leaders and thus undermining Indigenous spiritual autonomy. The forced division limited shared religious ceremonies and traditions that spanned multiple Indigenous groups.

Prohibition of Mixed Marriages Act of 1949 and Immorality Act of 1950

These acts restricted marriages and relationships between Europeans and non-Europeans. They affected familial and spiritual bonds that crossed racial lines. They led to family separations and reinforced racial divides, complicated the spiritual cohesion within communities that had previously integrated mixed cultural and spiritual practices. Marriages between Indigenous and European individuals sometimes incorporated elements of both spiritual practices. By prohibiting these unions, the laws also prohibited the potential blending and coexistence of spiritual practices, stifling the cultural exchange that could have fostered a hybridized spiritual resilience.

Population Registration Act of 1950

This Act’s racial categorization imposed an identity framework on Indigenous Peoples that limited their ability to identify spirituality within their cultural norms. Forced identity classifications often severed spiritual ties, as individuals were pressured to conform to state-imposed identities that could conflict with their Indigenous spiritual

beliefs. Moreover, led to internal and familial conflicts regarding spiritual identity. Indigenous individuals who were reclassified away from their spiritual community faced ostracization, leading to spiritual alienation and the erosion of communal spiritual practices.

The Separate Representation of Voters Act of 1951

This facilitated exclusion of certain Indigenous groups from voting, this Act limited Indigenous participation in political decisions that affected their cultural and spiritual practices. Political representation for Indigenous spiritual leaders or groups was non-existent, limiting any influence they could have in preserving or promoting Indigenous spiritual interests. Exclusion from civic participation restricted Indigenous communities' ability to protect sacred sites, rituals, and practices that were integral to their spirituality. This lack of representation stymied any legislative resistance to policies that undermined their spiritual traditions. Criminalized traditional rituals, promoted Christian missionary efforts, restricted access to culturally relevant education, and fragmenting ethnic groups, these laws aimed to dismantle the spiritual foundation of Indigenous communities. The laws not only stigmatized Indigenous spirituality but also eroded the traditional structures that sustained spiritual life. They created an environment where Indigenous spirituality was marginalized or criminalized. This suppression left lasting impacts and fragmented spiritual identities. Today traditional authority has diminished. Imposing foreign religious frameworks continue to shape the cultural landscape of Indigenous communities in post-colonial South Africa.

Colonial Systematic Innovation, and Growth Potential Sabotage of Indigenous South African

This analysis is drawn historic legislations, illustrating how colonial laws suppressed traditional economic agency, stifled innovation, and limited the growth potential of Indigenous populations by concentrating resources and opportunities within the white population. Effectively excluded Indigenous people from economic advancement.

Natives Land Act of 1913

This Act limited land ownership for Indigenous communities to just 7% of South Africa's land, later increased to 13%. The restriction confined Indigenous populations to designated "reserves," which were often less fertile and lacked economic resources, effectively reducing the agricultural productivity and economic independence of Indigenous farmers. When they removing land as a means of wealth creation and economic security, the Act forced Indigenous people into a cycle of poverty, making them economically dependent on wage labor in white-owned farms, industries, and mines. This severely curtailed Indigenous innovation and growth potential, as it restricted access to land-based resources that could be leveraged for economic development.

Urban Areas Act of 1923

This Act established separate urban areas for white and non-white populations, pushed Indigenous people into peripheral townships or "locations" with limited access to urban economic hubs. Indigenous individuals were required permits to live and work in "white" areas. This restricted access to better-paying jobs and entrepreneurial opportunities in the city. The goal was to restrict access to where the majority of economic activities occurred. This ensured Indigenous people's economic mobility and professional growth was under stringent control. To this day Indigenous population is separated and live reduced access to trade, services, and marketplaces.

The goal was to stifle Indigenous entrepreneurship and limited participation in the urban economy- to this day.

Native Administration Act of 1927

This Act gave the government control over all Indigenous affairs, that included economic activities within reserves. The state regulated Indigenous labor and wages. Often to the detriment of Indigenous workers. They were underpaid and exploited in comparison to white workers. They used centralized control to ensure government stifled Indigenous economic autonomy. Thus enforced policies that discouraged independent economic systems within Indigenous communities. This act hindered the growth of local economies and deprived communities of the opportunity to innovate or develop self-sustaining industries.

The Wage Act of 1925

The Wage Act allowed for racial wage disparities. It legally permitted lower wages for Indigenous workers compared to white workers performing the same jobs. This legislation institutionalized economic inequality. It ensured that Indigenous workers were confined to lower socioeconomic classes with limited purchasing power and savings potential. Restricted wages curtailed Indigenous people's capacity to accumulate wealth, invest in property, or develop business ventures. The wage gap fostered a cycle of poverty and dependency. To this day the impact of this act on obstruction of Indigenous communities from achieving economic progress and pursuing innovations that required capital investment.

The Mines and Works Act of 1911 (Amended in 1926)

This Act restricted skilled mining jobs to white workers. The act reserved low-paying, labor-intensive positions for Indigenous workers. Indigenous people were effectively barred from obtaining higher-paid positions that required skills development, training, and upward mobility. The limitation on skilled jobs prevented Indigenous

workers from gaining valuable expertise or advancing within industries. This stifled individual growth potential and curbed the development of Indigenous expertise in economically vital sectors like mining and engineering.

Group Areas Act of 1950

This Act designated specific urban and rural areas for different racial groups. This led to forced removals and relocations of Indigenous communities. Indigenous people were displaced from economically viable areas and resettled in locations with fewer resources and economic opportunities. Forced relocations disrupted Indigenous businesses and severed access to established customer bases. The Act hindered Indigenous entrepreneurship and innovation. Isolated communities from commercial markets. This allowed colonial project of concentrating resources within white-designated areas. And restricted Indigenous access to markets and financial institutions.

The Reservation of Separate Amenities Act of 1953

This Act mandated separate public facilities for different races. This resulted to underfunded amenities and resources for Indigenous people. Indigenous communities were excluded from quality facilities such as libraries, business districts, and recreational areas. To this day the spatial legacy still stifle creativity and restrict access to spaces that could support economic and intellectual growth. The separation from essential resources limited Indigenous access to knowledge, innovation networks, and commercial hubs. They were confined to economically isolated areas that hindered economic development and stifled the potential for collective growth.

The Bantu Education Act of 1953

This Act limited the education curriculum for Indigenous students to vocational subjects deemed suitable for manual labor. Indigenous students were denied access to subjects like mathematics, science, and business, which were critical for economic advancement and innovation. By design, this Act curtailed the development of skills

that would enable Indigenous people to compete in skilled labor markets or establish businesses. The restricted education prevented economic empowerment and perpetuated dependency on low-wage jobs, impeding the growth of Indigenous entrepreneurial spirit and innovation.

Pass Laws Act of 1952

The Pass Laws restricted the movement of Indigenous people. The act required them to carry passes to enter certain areas. This law limited Indigenous workers to employment options within designated zones. It confined them to low-wage, labor-intensive jobs and prevented access to broader job markets. Indigenous workers faced fines, imprisonment, or deportation for violating pass laws. The disrupted job stability prevented families from establishing economic security. The economic instability fostered by pass laws undermined growth potential. Obstructed long-term financial planning within Indigenous households.

Promotion of Bantu Self-Government Act of 1959

This Act designated certain regions as “homelands” for specific Indigenous ethnic groups. Further isolated Indigenous communities from the national economy. Homelands were underfunded. They lacked essential infrastructure and resources for economic development. The coloniser created economically isolated homelands through this Act. This enabled the coloniser to ensure Indigenous communities were precluded from engaging in the broader South African economy. The homelands were economically dependent on the colonial government. As such the act afforded restricted ability to develop industries, innovate, or engage in economic growth outside government allowances.

The Natives Resettlement Act of 1954

This Act enabled the government to forcibly relocate Indigenous people from urban areas deemed desirable for white residents. Indigenous businesses and homes were demolished, displaced families and disrupted community-based economic activities. The forced relocations dissolved Indigenous economic networks, destroyed small

businesses. This destroyed accumulated wealth and led to economic disempowerment. These disruption halted Indigenous entrepreneurship and innovation. Colonised people were left to start over in under-resourced areas.

Colonial Systematic Incitement of Conflict

This highlights how colonial laws that fostered an environment where Indigenous People resistance, uprisings, or even civil conflict could be incited.

Native Land Act of 1913

The act restricted Indigenous land ownership to designated "reserves". As it dispossessed many Indigenous families of their ancestral lands. It pushed them into overcrowded and under-resourced areas. Denied them land ownership rights. This was deliberate brewing of longstanding grievances and resentment toward colonial authorities. The incitement ensured Indigenous People lost farming lands and access to natural resources. Fostered environments that left Indigenous communities impoverished and economically dependent on low-wage labor. This economic deprivation, coupled with forced relocations was orchestrated to steer social unrest and resentment to incite resistance, conflict, riots, massacre, wars, genocide and race cleansing. Then turn around, write history as statistics that were killed by pandemics and lack immunity to diseases that came in South Africa with settlers.

Urban Areas Act of 1923

This Act, similarly to Native Land Act of 1913 restricted Indigenous people's movement in urban centres. It required them to live in designated townships or locations, separate from white neighbourhoods. Indigenous people were required to carry permits and faced arrest if found in white areas without one. Created a sense of surveillance and control that bred resentment. Positioning them as easy targets of all forms of violence. The substandard living conditions in townships that led to health issues, overcrowding, and poverty. These conditions hard efforts of the

colonial system to frustrate and anger Indigenous people. This was strategic heightening of civil disobedience, organized protests, and violent resistance as a reaction to the state abuse.

Pass Laws Act of 1952

The pass laws required all Indigenous people over a certain age to carry identification that restricted their movement. The laws' enforcement was often brutal, with frequent arrests, beatings, and humiliation for pass law violations. The pass laws became a focal point of Indigenous resistance and a powerful symbol of colonial repression. The frustration and anger toward these laws contributed to multiple uprisings, including the 1960 Sharpeville Massacre, where police killed 69 unarmed protesters. Such incidents deepened resentment, sparking nationwide protests and clashes.

Native Administration Act of 1927

This Act centralized government control over Indigenous communities, often imposing state-appointed leaders who were loyal to the government rather than community-chosen leaders. They undermined the legitimate Indigenous authority. This created a sense of injustice and alienation among Indigenous communities. The government disrupted traditional governance structures to foster discontent and anger among Indigenous people. This was fuelling the likelihood of organized resistance against what was violation and abuse.

Bantu Education Act of 1953

This Act forced Indigenous children into an education system that was vastly inferior to that provided for white children, focusing primarily on preparing them for manual labor rather than intellectual or professional advancement. This was a deliberate limitation on education and professional growth. Well thought to harbour anger among Indigenous youth. This led to a strong sense of injustice. This educational suppression incited frustration and contributed to student uprising. Fermented into the 1976 Soweto Uprising, where students protested against the forced use of

Afrikaans in schools. Ultimately the colonial long desired violent clashes with police came to flourishing. Colonial system could not hesitate to release gun powder of live ammunition to 20 000 little innocent boys and girls in school uniform. 7 200 children were detained under emergency regulations. 3,907 were injured. This massacre recorded more than 700 unarmed under 23 year olds that lost their precious lives while wearing their school uniform. This is just one among many brutal murder of Indigenous people by what characterised itself as blood thirst colonial system. This is to this kind of violence penetrated colonial system against colonised black community- that everyone expect CODESA, Democratic Constitution, TRC and 30 years of Democratic Government- that must be accepted as adequate mediation. We need a far more inclusive mediation than the white wash mediation we have be offered thus far.

Suppression of Communism Act of 1950

This Act broadly defined "communism" to include any form of resistance or dissent against apartheid policies. Indigenous leaders, activists, and movements opposing apartheid were frequently labeled as communist and subsequently arrested, banned, or exiled. They criminalized dissent and pushed anti-apartheid movements to operate underground. They led to the formation of more radical and militant groups. The suppression of peaceful opposition was deliberate conversion of moderate leaders into turn radicals to justify brutality against Africans.

Group Areas Act of 1950

This Act was passed to designate specific areas for different racial groups. Used to force the relocation of Indigenous communities. Bulldozed the entire neighbourhoods. This includes the destruction of communities like Sophiatown created intense anger and resentment among those forcibly removed. The uprooting of families and communities led to psychological trauma and intense provocation. The system invested massive resources to politicise black society. Inflicted massive trauma that compelled young and old to organize and protest. Through these colonial efforts children were forced into defiance of authorities. Dispossessed

communities had to search means and way to reclaim their rights and resist further exploitation.

Riotous Assemblies Act of 1956

The Act prohibited gatherings of more than 10 people if deemed a threat to public peace. It aimed to prevent Indigenous communities from organizing protests or gatherings. This was an attempt by government to project it feared resistance. While this was ia clamp down to peaceful assembly. With the goal to force Indigenous people to meet in secret. With the aim to push them to adopt more radical measures to voice their grievances. The restriction incited underground organizing, increased frustration, and led to the formation of liberation groups like the African National Congress's (ANC) military wing, Umkhonto we Sizwe, which resorted to armed resistance.

Separate Representation of Voters Act of 1951

This Act stripped Indigenous and mixed-race populations of any meaningful political representation, creating a legislative environment where they had no voice or influence over the laws and policies that governed them. Deprived of political recourse. Indigenous people felt that peaceful channels of change were unavailable to them. The lack of representation contributed to the view that resistance, including protest and militant opposition was the only viable means of challenging oppressive laws.

Public Safety Act of 1953 and Criminal Law Amendment Act of 1953

These Acts granted the government sweeping powers to declare states of emergency and suppress protests, including the use of deadly force. Any form of protest could be harshly punished, including with imprisonment, whipping, and even capital punishment. The severe consequences for peaceful protest led to an increase in underground resistance and the growth of militant anti-apartheid groups. The brutal repression of Indigenous protests hardened resistance movements, fostering more intense and organized conflict against apartheid.

The Promotion of Bantu Self-Government Act of 1959

This Act created separate “Bantustans” or homelands for specific Indigenous ethnic groups, enforcing artificial ethnic divisions to weaken unity among Indigenous populations. The artificial divisions fostered resentment between ethnic groups as resources were unevenly distributed among different Bantustans. This Act incited internal conflicts and tension, weakening Indigenous communities’ ability to unite against the apartheid state, and indirectly promoting distrust and division.

Sabotage Act of 1962

This Act expanded the government’s power to imprison or execute those suspected of “sabotage,” which included any act against colonial policies. Many Indigenous activists and leaders were prosecuted under this Act. Given harsh sentences. The harsh penalties and blanket criminalization of dissent was just a radicalization mechanism of the colonial system. This was reinforcement of inciting armed struggle as a form of resistance. All these efforts, collectively were just pure disruption of peace. Motivated by the quest of colonisers to be the majority of the country. And South Africa would have not been the first country to experience that type of colonisation.

Patterns of Colonial Abuse

Colonialism in South Africa systematically subjected Indigenous populations to centuries of abuse characterized by physical, emotional, psychological, sexual, and financial oppression. These abuses, driven by the colonizers’ pursuit of global dominance and resource acquisition, extended beyond individual harm, permeating families, communities, and the nation. Fueled by industrial capitalism’s demand for resources and labor, colonizers reduced Indigenous populations to cheap labor for mining, agriculture, and plantation economies. This exploitation underscored a quest

for self-actualization by the colonizers at the expense of African societies, leaving lasting structural damage.

Mediating the conflicts arising from colonialism necessitates a comprehensive understanding of its deep-rooted and widespread impacts. Colonized populations often lack detailed inventories of colonial benefits accrued by the colonizers or the full magnitude of harm caused to individuals, families, and societies. This gap leaves post-colonial nations vulnerable, without risk assessments or resilience plans to counter colonial legacies. Moreover, the colonized often struggle to identify colonial agents, enabling the continuation of exploitative systems.

Despite the introduction of constitutional frameworks, such as South Africa's Bill of Rights, to empower victims of colonial abuse, the past three decades demonstrate that these measures have been insufficient to dismantle the systemic legacies of colonization.

Negotiation

Negotiation, a cornerstone of Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR), involves parties with opposing interests engaging in direct or mediated discussions to manage and resolve disputes. In South Africa, the *Convention for a Democratic South Africa (CODESA)* negotiations were a critical step in transitioning from apartheid to democracy, rooted in addressing colonial abuse. Negotiations are typically characterized by informality, confidentiality, and a focus on fostering mutually beneficial outcomes. However, the success of negotiations depends on good faith and balanced power dynamics, both of which were contentious during CODESA.

CODESA required South African negotiators to balance competing liberal and socialist visions of sovereignty. Liberal theorists defined sovereignty as a state's ability to control activities within its borders, while realists viewed it as the authority to make decisive, authoritative policies. These ideological conflicts influenced the negotiating agenda, often forcing African delegates into defensive positions to prove their commitment to liberal democratic principles.

Challenges in the Negotiation Process

The asymmetry of power among negotiating parties at CODESA disadvantaged African representatives. Colonial governments had historically been authoritative, privileging and enriching select communities while disenfranchising the majority. This imbalance carried into negotiations, as the concessions African delegates secured were often limited by external pressures and internal divisions. Consequently, issues of colonial abuse and systemic inequality were insufficiently addressed.

Negotiation dynamics also revealed structural weaknesses:

- Disparities between negotiating parties rendered Africans inadequately represented, leading to agreements perceived as inequitable.
- Without neutral third-party facilitation, negotiations often favored more powerful parties, undermining trust and balanced outcomes.
- Negotiations could be used as a delaying mechanism to preserve colonial privileges or avoid substantial reform.

The resultant agreements, including the controversial Sunset Clause, have since faced significant criticism. While the negotiations facilitated a peaceful transition, they left unresolved many pressing issues stemming from centuries of colonial abuse.

The Sunset Clause and Ongoing Divisions

The Sunset Clause, designed as a temporary measure to preserve stability, is now a focal point of dissent. Three decades later, ideological divisions between neoliberal and socialist factions in South Africa highlight the limitations of the CODESA agreements. These unresolved disputes underscore the inherent risks of negotiation processes that lack enforceable safeguards and neutral oversight.

Negotiation, while a vital tool for conflict resolution, cannot guarantee trust or equitable outcomes when foundational imbalances persist. The absence of

mechanisms to ensure fairness and accountability limits the potential for transformative change.

South Africa stands at a crossroads where the effectiveness of past negotiation frameworks is under scrutiny. To address the enduring legacies of colonial abuse, future negotiations must prioritize:

1. Involving third parties to ensure balanced representation and equitable outcomes.
2. Incorporating detailed assessments of harm caused by colonialism to inform reparative justice mechanisms.
3. Embedding trust-building measures into negotiation frameworks to overcome centuries of systemic mistrust.
4. Ensuring that historically marginalized voices are heard and represented at every level.

Negotiation alone cannot resolve the complexities of South Africa's colonial legacy. However, by reimagining these processes to reflect fairness, accountability, and inclusivity, the nation can pave the way for lasting reconciliation and social cohesion.

Arbitration

Following South Africa's transition from colonial governance to democracy, the Truth and Reconciliation Commission (TRC) was established to address the systemic injustices and crimes committed under colonial and apartheid regimes. These crimes included dispossession, segregation, oppression, torture, mass violence, and economic deprivation. The TRC, formed under the *Promotion of National Unity and Reconciliation Act* (PNURA) No. 34 of 1995, aimed to foster reconciliation and healing by documenting atrocities and offering amnesty for politically motivated offences.

The Role of the Interim Constitution of 1993

The 1993 Interim Constitution laid the groundwork for reconciliation, including an "epilog" under the heading "National Unity and Reconciliation." Though not officially part of the constitutional text, this annex was widely regarded as carrying the same legal weight. It articulated a vision of moving from a divided, conflict-ridden past to a future grounded in human rights, democracy, and peaceful coexistence.

The epilog emphasized reconciliation over vengeance, reparations over retaliation, and *Ubuntu* (compassion and humanity) over victimization. Parliament translated these principles into the PNURA, which in turn provided the legal framework for the TRC. This framework sought to grant amnesty for politically motivated crimes, aiming to heal victims and address the grievances of colonization and apartheid. However, the TRC's outcomes and recommendations remain contentious, with many victims feeling excluded or inadequately represented.

Evaluating TRC as an ADR Mechanism

The TRC has often been categorized as a form of Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR), particularly conciliation. While ADR traditionally includes arbitration, mediation, and negotiation, the TRC's process does not fully align with the principles of arbitration due to the following. In arbitration, disputing parties voluntarily empower neutral arbitrators to determine a binding or non-binding resolution. By contrast, the TRC was imposed as a statutory process, and victims had no say in appointing commissioners or determining the scope of its mandate.

Limited Scope of Authority

Arbitration awards require enforceability, often through judicial systems. The TRC's recommendations, though grounded in the PNURA, lacked enforceability and failed to compel reparative actions for victims, such as financial compensation or social

justice reforms. While arbitration ensures neutrality, the TRC's composition and leadership raised concerns about impartiality. Archbishop Desmond Tutu, though highly respected, lacked legal training, which detracted from the procedural rigor expected of arbitration or ADR mechanisms. The TRC's terms of reference limited its focus to crimes committed between 1960 and 1994, excluding earlier colonial atrocities. This narrow scope failed to address grievances dating back to 1652, leaving unresolved a significant portion of historical injustices.

Revisiting Conciliation and Mediation

Although the TRC did not meet arbitration's procedural standards, it aligns more closely with conciliation and mediation. Conciliation aims to foster dialogue and propose solutions, often guided by a proactive conciliator. The TRC sought to reconcile victims and perpetrators by fostering a national dialogue, though its limited authority to enforce its recommendations hampered its success. Conciliation's strength lies in preventing conflict escalation and promoting social cohesion. However, in the case of the TRC, the conciliatory approach often prioritized political stability over victim justice, leading to perceptions of unresolved grievances. This trade-off highlights the need for ADR mechanisms that are transparent, participatory, and accountable to all stakeholders.

Trust Deficits and the TRC's Legacy

The TRC was a significant step toward post-apartheid reconciliation, but its inability to enforce reparations or resolve underlying conflicts left a trust deficit. This mistrust extends across South African society—between citizens, the government, and institutions. The lingering effects of colonial divide-and-rule strategies exacerbate these divides, undermining efforts to achieve social cohesion and national unity.

To address South Africa's persistent trust deficit, this article proposes reimagining ADR mechanisms with the following principles. It is important to ensure all victims of

colonial injustices are heard. The coloniser must be open to participate on accountable processes to rebuild public trust. For purpose of enforcing resolution, it is important to integrate ADR outcomes with judicial systems to ensure implementation of reparations and justice. Resources are needed to equip legal professionals and policymakers with necessarily expertise to address conflicts rooted in historical injustices. There must be willingness to expand parameters of inquiry to include colonial-era crimes, recognizing their enduring impact.

CONCLUSION

Rebuilding trust is the cornerstone of resolving historical injustices and fostering a society capable of sustained peace and equitable development. In South Africa—and globally—centuries of colonization have left a legacy of distrust that undermines efforts at reconciliation and growth. Trust reconstruction requires moving beyond traditional methods of conflict resolution that have consistently failed to address the root causes of inequality and discord.

To South Africans, this means prioritizing inclusive and transformative policies that bridge racial and economic divides. South Africa must shift from frameworks that focus on unsustainable individualised wealth accumulation to systems that promote generational upward social mobility. Legal and policy reforms should embrace restorative justice, acknowledgement of historic wrongs by colonisers. Make provision of mechanisms for healing and trust reconstruction post-colonial conflicts.

Calls for Empire's paradigm shift must be understood in proper context. The context began when coloniser used combat to invade and colonise a particular territory that was foreign to them. The coloniser seized power and authority over the conquered territory. 400 years later the coloniser is still positioned as custodian of the territory. Through education and political system that has been established by the coloniser, public is successfully led to believe colonisation has completely ended. This public

belief makes the public to be complacent with covert colonisation. What is even worse is that public naiveness is not only aiding perpetual colonisation, defend it.

As such the coloniser is involve in every political activity occurring in all their colonies. Colonial involvement in political affairs of sovereign territory is indicative of refusal to release colonial power and authority. As purported by political and education that colonisation ended. This purported end of colonisation was a decision of UN. UN charter was developed by the coloniser. Subsequently, colonisation came to an abrupt end in compliance to UN declaration. Therefore, safe to conclude that the end of colonisation was in fact voluntary. The coloniser had full discretion in how they choose to end colonisation.

As such the coloniser selected to unbundle colonisation into elements of colonisation. The unbundling of colonisation created colonial power and colonial authority. Colonizer branded colonial power as sovereignty. NATO was then established through UN for purposes of protecting sovereignty. As such NATO was set up to protect colonies on behalf of the coloniser. Supplementary to UN and NATO additional international institutions such as USAID, WHO, WB, IMF, INICEF, Global Ranking Agencies etc. These organisation function as covert colonial agents (or proxy). They exert colonial authority in the form of conditions for recognition for access to economic network. The post world war II international organisations are vectors of colonial authority. The international organisations define policies that are prerequisite for sovereign recognition. The international organisations pen the details of prerequisite policies in the form of conventions and protocols. Sovereign states are coerced to comply- in the pretence of protecting human rights. The fundamental human right is equality. But the founding principles such as VITO powers reflect their inability to uphold the values they claim to promote. The policies of these international organisations are designed to dictate who rules, when s/he rules, how s/he rule, and why s/he rules. This renders conventions and protocols as colonial authority and who, when, how, and why s/he rules is a rented power of colonial rule with or without his or her knowledge. These conventions and protocols must be subjected to national scrutiny. They must be measured through traditional values of

Ubuntu. They must pass the test of family, honesty, fairness, mutual respect, and empowerment. Global institutions start understanding the importance of a family. The day their policies start focusing on strengthening and empowering families. Is the day the world will be free from conflicts, trust deficit and equal. Every species is born in a family. Family is the closest way to secure people support for success. The western obsession with individualism is a feudal culture. It is primitive. It is colonial. It is designed to perpetuate everything that is wrong- mistrust, disputes, conflicts, inequalities, slavery and violence.

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